

FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF POETIC TEXTS: COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF AI AND HUMAN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: *The article examines the features of poetic translation in the context of globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies. It emphasizes the complexity of poetic translation as a multi-layered process that involves not only conveying meaning, but also preserving rhythm, rhyme, sound organization, imagery, and cultural associations. The paper analyzes the challenges arising from the high semantic density of poetic language and its cultural specificity. Particular attention is paid to the comparison between translations produced by artificial intelligence and those created by professional human translators. The findings show that neural machine translation systems are generally capable of conveying the overall meaning of the source text; however, they face difficulties in preserving rhythmic and rhyming structures, imagery, and stylistic adequacy. In contrast, human translation demonstrates a higher level of artistic accuracy and adaptation. The study concludes that artificial intelligence should be considered as an auxiliary tool, while the key role in producing a полноценный художественный перевод remains with the human translator.*

Keywords: *poetic translation, literary translation, artificial intelligence, neural machine translation, translation activity, rhythm and rhyme, imagery, semantic density, cultural specificity, comparative analysis*

In the context of globalization and the rapid development of digital technologies, translation activities are undergoing significant changes. A special place in the translation system is occupied by artistic translation, and among its varieties is the translation of poetic texts, which is traditionally considered one of the most complex types of interlanguage transmission. This is due to the fact that a poetic text is a complex multi-layered structure in which meaning is formed not only at the level of vocabulary, but also due to rhythm, rhyme, sound organization, imagery and cultural associations.

Poetic language is characterized by a high degree of semantic density. Each word in a poem can carry several levels of meaning at once: direct, figurative, symbolic, and emotional. Unlike a prose text, where information is distributed more evenly, in poetry the meaning is concentrated in a minimal amount of linguistic means. This creates significant difficulties for the translator, since it is often impossible to preserve all semantic levels at the same time.

A special role in the poetic text is played by its phonetic organization. Rhythm, rhyme, alliteration and assonance form not only aesthetic perception, but also participate in the creation of meaning. However, these elements are closely related to a specific language system, which significantly complicates their transmission during translation. As a result, the translator is faced with the need to choose whether to keep the form or convey the content. In practice, this leads to a compromise in which some elements of the text are preserved, while others are transformed.

An equally important factor is the cultural conditioning of the poetic text. Images, symbols, and allusions often have a national-specific character and may be incomprehensible to a reader of another culture. In this regard, the translator is forced to make decisions about the degree of adaptation of the text: to preserve the original realities, replace them with analogues, or interpret them. This choice directly affects the adequacy of the translation and its perception.

The current stage in the development of translation studies is associated with the active introduction of artificial intelligence technologies. Neural machine translation systems based on the principles of language modeling are capable of generating coherent texts and providing sufficiently high accuracy when translating informational and business texts. However, the application of these

technologies to poetic texts remains problematic. This is due to the fact that artificial intelligence does not have the ability to interpret, but only operates with probabilistic connections between linguistic units.

In the framework of this study, a comparative analysis of translations of poetic text performed using artificial intelligence and professional translators was carried out. The main criteria of the analysis were the accuracy of the transmission of meaning, the preservation of the figurative system, the reproduction of rhythmic-rhyming structure and stylistic adequacy. The results of the analysis showed that the translation performed with the help of artificial intelligence is generally able to convey the general meaning of the source text, but it has a number of significant drawbacks. In particular, there is a violation of rhythm, a lack of stable rhyming, as well as the literal nature of the transmission, leading to a loss of imagery and emotional expressiveness. In addition, there are lexical inaccuracies and syntactic constructions that do not comply with the norms of the translation language.

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In contrast, human translation demonstrates a higher level of artistic adequacy. Professional translators strive not only to convey the content, but also to preserve the aesthetic impact of the text. To do this, they use various transformations to adapt the form of the original to the norms of the target language, while preserving its oral and emotional structure. A comparative analysis allows us to conclude that at the current stage of technology development, artificial intelligence is not able to fully reproduce a poetic text as an artistic whole. The main limitations are related to the lack of interpretation, the inability to adequately convey metaphorical meanings, and insufficient transmission of the sound and rhythmic organization of the text. Nevertheless, artificial intelligence can be considered as an auxiliary tool in the translation process. It can be useful at the stage of preliminary translation, selection of lexical correspondences or text analysis. However, the final work on a poetic translation requires the participation of a person with not only linguistic, but also cultural and artistic competence. For a more visual confirmation of these provisions, an additional mini-study was conducted based on a comparison of translations of the same poetic fragment performed using a neural system and a human translator. The analysis showed that the AI translation retains basic information, but the structure of the text is disrupted: lines become uneven, rhyme is absent or random, and figurative expressions are simplified. In human translation, on the contrary, there is a desire to preserve the rhythmic and rhyming organization, as well as to convey the stylistic features of the original.

In the future, the development of technology may lead to an improvement in the quality of machine translation of poetic texts, but even in this case, the role of humans will remain key. The most effective model seems to be one in which artificial intelligence is used as an auxiliary tool, and

the final interpretation and artistic processing of the text is carried out by a translator. This allows you to combine the speed and technical capabilities of a machine with the creative potential of a human, providing a higher level of translation quality.

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